

Overview of GRACE – A Database System for Analysis of Multiple Genomes*

Ray Hagstrom* George S. Michaels† Ross Overbeek* Morgan Price*
Ronald Taylor†

*Mathematics and Computer Science Division
Argonne National Laboratory
Argonne, IL 60439-4801

†Division of Computer Research and Technology
National Institutes of Health
Bethesda, MD 20892

Abstract

*In previous work, we developed a database system to support analysis of the *E. coli* genome. That system provided a pidgin-English query facility, rudimentary pattern-matching capabilities, and the ability to rapidly extract answers to a wide variety of questions about the organization of the *E. coli* genome. To enable the comparative analysis of the genomes from different species, we have designed and implemented a new prototype database system, called GRACE. GRACE extends our earlier effort by incorporating a set of curator's tools that facilitate the incorporation of physical and genetic data, together with the results of genomic organization analysis, into a common database system. Additional tools for extracting, manipulating, and analyzing data are planned. This paper is the first published overview of GRACE.*

maps as defined by genetic linkage analysis, genome mapping data such as clone hybridization results, restriction enzyme fragment mapping (high-resolution maps from clones and electrophoresis fragment maps for a chromosome), and physical data from DNA sequencing.

Providing flexible access to such diverse data presents a challenging problem in data representation. In earlier work on the *E. coli* genome [1-3], we designed a database based on the programming language Prolog. We chose Prolog because of its inherent relational database characteristics, powerful query capabilities, and ability for rapid prototyping. After we added a pidgin-English query interface, biologists were able to begin analyzing the combined clone, physical map, sequence fragment, and genetic data.

1 Introduction

With the current advances in molecular biology and genome science, the ability to perform comparative analysis of the genome organization between species is rapidly becoming a reality. Such comparative analysis requires access to a variety of genomic map information [4]. This map information includes genetic

To enable comparative analysis of genomes from different species, we have designed and implemented a new prototype database called GRACE that integrates data from such multiple genomes. The GRACE system initially will help those users attempting to organize and curate genomic data, including maps, sequences, and alignments. The present version has pidgin-English access to a wide variety of types of data relating to a collection of genomes. Future versions will have a graphical user interface. Ultimately, we envision that GRACE will be used both by research biologists and by teachers in classroom instruction.

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1.1 Components of the GRACE System

The GRACE system is currently composed of a number of distinct tools that we are integrating into a coherent framework:

1. A set of tools designed to extract data from archival databases (such as GenBank [5], EMBL [6], and PIR [7]). These tools reformat the data into Prolog for insertion into our database.
2. A Prolog database that supports flexible access to the data, along with a toolkit designed to support curatorial functions (such as redundancy control, recognition of similarity, meld support, and positioning of sequence fragments on chromosomes). There is also a pidgin-English command framework for common queries. The parser that implements this pidgin-English interface is specific to GRACE.
3. GenoGraphics [8], a system that supports visual display and reasoning about the data in the Prolog database. (Note that GenoGraphics can function as a stand-alone tool, accepting data from outside the Prolog database as long as it is properly formatted. GenoGraphics has its own internal database system, separate from the Prolog database. We transfer data from the Prolog database to this database when we want visual display.) It can produce displays of physical maps, genetic maps, cytogenetic maps, sequence fragments, attached features, GC content, and a variety of other types of data. In addition, it includes facilities for searching sequence for patterns (not as sophisticated as what can be done in the Prolog database, but quite good) and for attaching comments to objects (including graphics images, a feature of interest in documenting specific curatorial decisions).

Each of these three components addresses a critical problem facing anyone attempting to curate or access genomic data. We will maintain basic documentation on all three components as they evolve.

1.2 Using GRACE

The GRACE system is intended to be used as follows. First, genomic data is extracted and reformatted into Prolog clauses, which constitute the "logical integration" of the data. This initial step converts data from available archival sources into a consistent representation that offers flexible access.

Then, using the tools offered by the Prolog database component, a curator goes through the following steps:

1. generation of a non-redundant data collection by removing redundant sequence fragments from the different data collections (often making decisions concerning which of several possible versions of the data to keep), and then
2. placing sequence fragments on locations or intervals of the relevant genome (using information in physical maps, genetic maps, and sequence similarity to related genomes). Clearly, issues relating to multiple versions of sequence fragments are controversial (when to keep alleles, when to discard possible sequencing errors, identification of included vector sequences, and so on). The proper handling of these "social" issues is not completely worked out yet. These are problems for a domain expert to decide. However, we are making every effort to produce a framework where such issues can be addressed in a productive manner.

Once an initial version of the data has been determined, a visual presentation of the integration is created by using GenoGraphics. We have found that numerous curatorial decisions are more easily made when the effects of such decisions can be visually summarized. (We are tightly integrating GenoGraphics to the Prolog database component. The flow of data from the Prolog database into GenoGraphics is already automated and simple, but options will be added so that the transfer will become even easier to perform for display of features on the genome that contain complex patterns.) Once an initial integration has been achieved, the curator can construct a variety of detailed GenoGraphic maps that visually portray many useful aspects of the data, including the distribution of interesting sequence features and the GC content of regions.

1.3 Availability

We are making stand-alone versions of GenoGraphics available in the public domain. These will be the main form of mass distribution of the combined data from multiple genomes. GenoGraphics runs both under MS-DOS on PCs and on Sun workstations under Unix and X-Windows. The MS-DOS version of GenoGraphics contains its own windowing environment and does not need Microsoft Windows.

We also plan to make the Prolog database, along with the GenoGraphics tool, available to labs capa-

ble of supporting the associated computational environment. (Unix is needed at present, together with Quintus Prolog and, as a matter of practicality, some sort of Unix shell such as Gnu-Emacs, which allows *post facto* access to the screen output stream; we are, however, actively pursuing the transfer of the Prolog database to a version of Prolog that runs under MS-DOS so that the entire GRACE system will run on an IBM PC or PC-clone.) The initial forms of this release will be of a system that is still openly viewed as a prototyping environment and will be intended for users that are comfortable with Unix workstation computing environments. Copies of the prototype system are available from the authors.

Since the GRACE system is in an initial and evolving stage, original users must be aware of the basic function of each of the distinct tools and how they interact. The remainder of this document addresses these points.

2 Converting Archived Data into the Prolog Representation

The conversion of archived data to GRACE system format is a three-step process.

1. GenBank or EMBL locus entries are converted to Prolog clause format. Essentially, each field of an entry (locus, definition, comment, features, etc.) is translated into one argument of a clause. Also, some information is extracted from the surrounding text and stored in separate arguments: the locus id, the (first) accession number, and the base listing concatenated together as one unbroken string, among others. The locus entries taken as input can be in any of four formats: NCBI GenBank, Intelligenetics GenBank, GCG GenBank, or EMBL. In addition, we are currently implementing the same sort of import/export facility to the new "acedb" database [9], which has been adopted by the *C. elegans* and *Arabidopsis thaliana* research communities.
2. Each feature and associated sequence from the feature table for each locus (now in Prolog format) is extracted and converted to Prolog clause format. The base sequence of the feature is analyzed and information is stored on whether (a) a join was used, (b) the sequence was an integer multiple of three, (c) the "direct" or "complement" strand was used, (d) a start codon begins the sequence, and (e) a stop codon appears before,

at, or immediately after the end of the sequence (or is missing entirely).

3. The Prolog-formatted locus entries and features are entered into the actual GRACE system by conversion into GRACE objects. Locus entries become objects of type "sequence_fragment". The original locus id is assigned as the unique id of each such object. Feature objects fall into many classes or types, depending on how they were labeled in the original feature table in the archived data. For example, a coding-sequence feature labeled "cds" in the feature table would be given the type "cds". Similarly, we would obtain these types: "mRNA", "tRNA", "prim_transcript", "misc.feature", "promoter", etc. If the feature describes a gene, the conversion program tries to automatically pull out the name of the gene from the associated note lines for that feature so that it may serve as the primary identifier. Otherwise, a unique number is assigned to the feature.

3 Format of the Prolog Database

At the present stage of GRACE's development, a curator is expected to have a basic understanding of how data is represented in the Prolog database. Eventually, we hope to hide as much of this detail as possible. We begin with some examples and then discuss the general form.

3.1 Examples of Data in Prolog Representation

clones:

format:

```
object(CloneId,Level,ListOfAttributes).
precisely_bound(ObjectId,
                 ListOfSubPiecesOfParent).
```

example:

```
object('[101]9E4'(clone,'E.coli'),0,
        [length(17100)]).
precisely_bound('[101]9E4'(clone,'E.coli'),
                 [to('EC1'(chromosome,'E.coli'),
                     387,17486)]).
```

(The value 'EC1' above denotes the first — and in this case sole — chromosome of *E. coli*. The chromosome

number is concatenated onto the genomic abbreviation 'EC' to form this identifier.)

restriction enzyme cutting sites (rsites):

```
object('EcoR5'(restriction_site),0,
      [site("GATATC"),cuts_at(3)]).
precisely_bound('EcoR5'(restriction_site),
               [to('EC1'(chromosome,'E.coli'),6800,
                  6805)]).
```

sequence fragments:

```
Example derived from a GenBank entry:
object('STYARALC'(sequence_fragment,
                'Salmonella'),0,[length(1286),
                                nuc_seq_ref(94290)]).
object('STYARALC'(sequence_fragment,
                'Salmonella'),1,[constituents(
                                [constituent('STYARALC',0,1285,
                                             direct,1286)])]).
imprecisely_bound('STYARALC'(sequence_fragment,
                        'Salmonella'), [to('SA1'(chromosome,
                                             'Salmonella'))]).
```

Example of a meld:

```
object(meld13(sequence_fragment,'Salmonella'),
       0,[length(5277),nuc_seq_ref(171681)]).
object(meld13(sequence_fragment,'Salmonella'),
       1,[constituents(
           [constituent('STYFLIG',0,2754,direct,2755),
            constituent('STYFLIHIJ',132,2653,
                        direct,2654)])]).
precisely_bound(meld13(sequence_fragment,
                       'Salmonella'),
               [to('SA1'(chromosome,'Salmonella'),
                  2023079,2028355)]).
```

A meld describes a sequence_fragment that is constructed from portions of a collection of sequence_fragments. Melds are also known as sequence contigs.

features:

```
object(aphC(cds,'Salmonella'),0,
      [note("alkyl hydroperoxide reductase
            C22 protein (aphC)",codon_start(1))].
precisely_bound(aphC(cds,'Salmonella'),
               [to('STYAHPCFA'(sequence_fragment,
                              'Salmonella'),165,719,direct)])).
```

(Note that if the last argument had been "complement" rather than "direct", it would have meant "take the subsequence of STYAHPCFA in the range 165 to

719, reverse the base string obtained, and then take the biological complement of the reversed string".)

mapped_genes:

```
object(atbB(mapped_gene,'Salmonella'),0,
      [position(7.60),map('Sanderson')]).
object(atbB(mapped_gene,'Salmonella'),1,
      [mnemonic("Attachment"),
       desc("attP27II; second attachment
            site for prophage P27"),
       refs("[410,412,418]")
      ]).
precisely_bound(atbB(mapped_gene,
                    'Salmonella'),[to('SA1'(chromosome,
                                        'Salmonella'),384238,384338)]).
```

(Not all mapped genes need to be thought of as bound to the chromosome at an approximate base pair position, but they should move to that state fairly rapidly.)

3.2 General Format

Facts describing objects in the Prolog database are of the form *object(Id, Level, [Attributes])*. These are referred to as 'object/3' clauses, since the name (in Prolog terminology, the "functor") of the clause is "object", and the clause has three arguments. There may be (and typically is) more than one object/3 clause associated with a given object. Such multiple clauses have the same *Id*, but differ in the *Level* and *Attributes* arguments. (The reasons for the parceling out of an object's data over more than one object/3 clause are described in Section 3.3.) The brackets ("[" "]") in the third argument above signify that we place a list of attributes (which consists of one or more members), rather than just one attribute, in that argument.

Facts constraining location of the object are placed in the form *precisely_bound(Id, [WhatItIsBoundTo])* or *imprecisely_bound(Id, [WhatItIsBoundTo])*. An object is precisely bound to a "containing" object (or set of objects) in which its relative position is known. The containing set would include more than one entry only for objects that are discontinuous pieces within a containing object (i.e., a gene with introns in a sequence fragment) or, in an even more general case, for objects that are composed of pieces from distinct "containing objects". (These will be rare.) In the case of precisely bound objects, the *WhatItIsBoundTo* entries will be of the form *to(Id, Beg, End)* or *to(Id, Beg, End, Direction)*, where *Beg* and *End* are offsets (in base pairs, no matter how approximate) and *Direction* will be ei-

ther 'direct' or 'complement'. *Id* will be the Id of the containing object (more on this below).

An object is imprecisely bound if the contained object occurs somewhere in the circumscribed interval. In the case of imprecisely bound objects, the *WhatItIsBoundTo* entries will be of the form *to(Id)* or *to(Interval)* where *Interval* is of the form *interval(Id, Beg, End)* or *interval(Point1, Point2)*, with *Beg* and *End* being offsets (again, in bp), and *Point1* and *Point2* points described by facts of the form *point(PointName, Id, Offset)*, where *PointName* is located as an *Offset* into *Id*.

In the current database, objects of most types have either one *precisely_bound/2* clause or one *imprecisely_bound/2* clause. However, there is no theoretical factor barring us from placing the same object onto multiple larger objects or placing an object at multiple locations on the same object (which is exactly what we do for restriction sites).

Our framework allows us to have a hierarchy of objects, with each object being precisely (or imprecisely) bound to a location in a larger object. At present, we typically have either a three-part or a two-part hierarchy: feature (or clone or *rsite*) bound to sequence fragment bound to chromosome (feature $\rightarrow$ sequence fragment $\rightarrow$ chromosome), or mapped gene (or *rsite*) bound to chromosome.

(Sequence fragments, which are objects themselves, of course, have just a two-part hierarchy: sequence fragment $\rightarrow$ chromosome. The largest source of sequence fragments for our database at present are the locus entries in the GenBank and EMBL databases, or melds thereof. For the *E. coli* genome, substantial additional information has come from the EcoSeqV and EcoGene databases compiled by Kenneth Rudd [10-11]. Genetic linkage data has been taken from the Bachmann *E. coli* map [12] and the Sanderson *S. typhimurium* map [13].

3.3 Efficiency Issues

When the built-in Prolog query-answering "engine" accesses a clause containing a string of characters, it must convert that string into another format for internal use. There is no way to shut off this automatic conversion. Therefore, to keep the response time of queries to the system as small as possible, we try to avoid accessing clauses containing long strings. One way to do this is to introduce levels in the definition of objects in order to segregate attributes into classes. The levels are numbered 0, 1, 2, ... The clauses corresponding to these levels occur in the appropriate sequence (*i* before *j* iff $i < j$). Attributes are

of the form *keyword(value)*. Attributes at level 0 typically have fairly small values (and are few in number); they should be just the most commonly referenced attributes. Longer attributes (such as "constituents" of a sequence fragment or "descriptions") are relegated to high levels. Our system is written so that the level 0 clause is tried first. If the desired data is not present in the list of Attributes in that clause, we then access the level 1 clause for the object, then the level 2 clause, and so on, until the query is either satisfied or we have run out of levels (clauses) to try for that object. We store long strings (such as, say, the comment field from a GenBank entry describing a sequence fragment) at higher levels (typically level 2).

A second technique that we have implemented to increase efficiency involves indexing. The Id of an object may include many "fields". An Id is intended to be an unambiguous designator of the object. The natural way to specify such an id would be *type(K1, K2, K3...)*, e.g., *prim_transcript(aphC, 'E.coli')*.

Unfortunately, this would incur an enormous performance penalty, due to the first-argument indexing scheme used in Prolog systems. (Since the type - *prim_transcript* in our example - could be expected to be duplicated many times, rather than being a unique case, response time will grow as the system searches through all the possibilities.) Hence, we try to use the most discriminating of the fields as the functor. For sequence fragments derived from GenBank, for example, this means using the GenBank locus id as the functor of an object's id.

The intent of these representational conventions is to leave us with an extremely flexible, extensible system. We believe that we will be able to absorb the complexity of GDB and GenBank into a single framework using these conventions.

4 Using the Prolog Database

The Prolog database offers access to integrated data across multiple genomes. It can be used to support curatorial activity, prepare maps for GenoGraphics, or to support comparative analysis of genomes. There are two basic levels of use: through a pidgin-English interface and with "raw Prolog." Since the most common use will be through the pidgin-English interface, we present a brief overview.

To gain access to the Prolog database, one simply types "GRACE" and the system should respond, after some initialization messages, with "|?-", which is the

Prolog prompt. The user then types "query.", which causes the system to initialize and respond with the pidgin-English prompt, "query:".

At such a prompt, the user types in a command. Each command can spread over multiple lines, but it is terminated when a period is the last character of a line. The system will attempt to parse the command and then respond appropriately. For example, following below is a record of a "session" composed of two simple queries. (Note that the query system first prints out the query, as it understands it, before executing it. This is useful as a check on what the system is actually doing, as compared to what the user might think it is doing. To conserve space, this part of the system response will be omitted in all later examples.)

```
query: print all sequence_fragments of Vaccinia.
```

```
print all sequence_fragments of Vaccinia
```

```
sequence_fragment VACCG of Vaccinia
  (location=chromosome VA1[0,191736]):
  accession_num: M35027
  constituents: VACCG[0,191736,direct]
  length: 191737
```

```
=====
query: print occurrences of pattern in VACCG.
```

```
print occurrences of pattern in
sequence_fragment VACCG of Vaccinia
```

```
pattern: p1=14...14 3...20 ~p1
```

```
----- 2 found -----
interval [16071,16112] of sequence_fragment
VACCG of Vaccinia
GCCGGTGTAATAGA ATTATATATATCTA TCTATTACACGGC
```

```
interval [130102,130134] of sequence_fragment
VACCG of Vaccinia
AAAAAACTATCTA TGCGG TAGATAGTTTTTT
```

The first query *print all sequence_fragments of Vaccinia*, caused the system to determine how many sequence fragments were included in the genome of *Vaccinia*. There was only one, VACCG (which covers the entire genome). The second query *print occurrences of pattern in VACCG*, caused the system to prompt for the particular pattern for which it should scan. Note that the end of the pattern is detected by an end-of-line (i.e., it is not delimited by a period). The pattern typed in above by the user requested a search for hairpins with perfect stems of length 14 and a cap (loop)

of 3 to 20 characters. GRACE found two matches to this pattern to report.

The general format for search patterns goes as follows. We think of a pattern as a sequence of pattern units, each of which can be (a) a string of DNA characters (including the codes to represent ambiguous characters), (b) a pattern unit that matches an arbitrary string of characters, where the length of the string varies between specified bounds, (c) a pattern unit that "matches" the complement of a string matched by a previous pattern unit, or (d) a pattern unit that matches a string identical to a previously matched pattern unit. Both of the last two types of pattern units allow one to specify an allowable number of mismatches, insertions, and deletions (which gives an "approximate" matching capability).

For example, we would think of the the following p-unit of a sequence pattern describing a hairpin nucleic acid structure:

```
p1=AYGG 3...5 ~p1 p1
```

as consisting of four subunits: *p1* (the pattern AYGG), followed by three to five bases of any composition, followed by the complement of *p1* (represented by *p1* prefixed with a tilde), followed by *p1* again.

Hence this pattern is capable of matching a sequence like ACGGTTCCGCCGTACGG. (ACGG fits *p1*'s AYGG pattern, TCCG falls within the allowed three to five arbitrary bases, CCGT fits the complement of *p1*, and ACGG fits the last *p1* subunit.)

The GRACE session is terminated with the command: *query: quit*.

The set of possible queries/commands will eventually be far richer than the current set (it will certainly include all of the query classes implemented in our previous *E. coli* database system).

As with our previous system, we believe that the easiest way to describe the set of allowable queries is by showing examples. Our hope is that the user with a specific query in mind will be able to mimic one of the examples (if not, the required functionality probably is not yet in the pidgin-English interface). So, here are typical examples, along with short explanations of what is produced. Formatted sequences and alignments in system responses are omitted in consideration of space.

(1) Retrieving the data for a gene. A sample query for the gene *fliC* goes as follows:

```
query: print fliC.
```

The response from the query interface is:

4 possible interpretations

- 1: print cds fliC of E.coli
- 2: print mapped_gene fliC of E.coli
- 3: print cds fliC of Salmonella
- 4: print mapped_gene fliC of Salmonella

Which would you like? [1]: 3

The system understands that there is more than one interpretation of the request, and allows the user to choose which is correct. Once a choice is made (the third interpretation is chosen in the above example), the following appears:

```
cds fliC of Salmonella
(location= *** multiple locs:
sequence_fragment STYFLICA[0,851] complement;
sequence_fragment STYFLID[0,63] complement):
mnemonic: Flagella
desc: H1; Flagellar synthesis;
      flagellin (filament structural protein);
      phase 1 flagellin gene
refs: [143,199,205,222,243,247,302,410,412,
       418,507,508]
```

(2) Finding data for a specific coding region (cds). The following interaction requests all information about the cds "A13L". Since there is only one database entry for A13L, there is no interpretation conflict to be resolved.

query: print the sequence of A13L.

The response from the query interface is:

```
cds A13L of Vaccinia
(location=
sequence_fragment VACCG[126535,
126747] complement)
note: A13L
codon_start: 1
0  ATGATTGGTA TTCTTTTGTT ...
50  CATCCTATAC TCGATGTATA ...
100 CAAGTCCGAA TTAAATTTCG ...
150 GTAAATAATC TGGAAAAGGA ...
200 ATCTTCTGTA TAA
```

(3) Retrieving the sequence around a specific point. To get the sequence that includes 20 bases on either side of the start for cds A13L, the following is entered:

query: print the sequence of the interval from query: the start of A13L - 20 to the end of query: A13L + 20.

The response from the query interface is:

```
interval [126515,126767,complement] of
sequence_fragment VACCG of Vaccinia
0  AGTGAAGTTA TTGTCAATAA ...
50  TGGCTAGCAG TTACCGTCGC ...
100 GAACTCACAA AATCCGAATC ...
150 AACCAAAAAA TACCAAGTTT ...
200 TCATGTATA ATCTAGTTAA ...
250 TTC
```

(4) Finding upstream and downstream regions relative to chromosome features. The following is an example of such a regional description, looking for the ten bases upstream of a feature:

query: print the sequence of upstream(A13L,10).

The response from the query interface is:

```
interval [126748,126757,complement] of
sequence_fragment VACCG of Vaccinia
0  TTGTCAATAA
```

(5) Finding common substrings. One of the earliest queries often made to compare similar regions between species involves looking for sequences in common in specific gene regions that are believed to have similar functions. The following is an example of such a request.

query: print all sequences of length at least query: 10 common to {aceA,aceE}.

The response from the query interface is:

9 possible interpretations

- 1: print all sequences of length at least 10 common to {cds aceA of E.coli, cds aceE of E.coli}
- 2: print all sequences of length at least 10 common to {cds aceA of E.coli, mapped_gene aceE of E.coli}

. (omitted)

Which would you like? [1]: 1

After the user makes her choice above, the following is displayed:

14 sequences in common in the following objects:
====

----- 1 -----
cds aceA of E.coli
(location=
sequence_fragment hydGecoM[14191,15495]
direct):
accession: EG10022
SwissProt: P05313

----- 2 -----
cds aceE of E.coli
(location=
sequence_fragment ampDecoM[4713,7373]
direct):
accession: EG10024
SwissProt: P06958

. (omitted)

TCGAAAAAAG length=10
positions in object 1 are [180]
positions in object 2 are [291]

(6) Searching sets of objects. The following interaction demonstrates how to use a pattern (in this case, a hairpin pattern) to search through the 20-base region surrounding the start of every cds feature defined for the Vaccinia genome. (Note that "occs" and "pat" are acceptable abbreviations for "occurrences" and "pattern", respectively.)

query: for each cds in Vaccinia \$X,
query: print occs of pat in the interval
query: from the start of \$X - 20 to
query: the start of \$X + 20.

The response is:

pattern: p1=7...7 3...8 ~p1
====<< context >>====
----- 1 -----
cds A10L of Vaccinia
(location=
sequence_fragment VACCG[122285,124960]
complement):
note: A10L
codon_start: 1

====
interval [2,23] of interval(VACCG
(sequence_fragment,Vaccinia),124940,124980,

complement)

TCATTTA ATACTAAA TAAATGA
. (omitted)

(7) Getting codon usage and n-mer decompositions. It is also possible to evaluate the simple statistics for nucleotide composition for a genome. The following interaction shows how to get both codon usage for the defined cds features of a genome and the full trinucleotide statistics.

query: print the codon usage of cds
query: in Vaccinia.

The response is:

number valid codons = 60974
number invalid codons = 0

alanine: 2310	3.79%
GCA: 690	1.13%
GCC: 409	0.67%
GCG: 440	0.72%
GCT: 771	1.26%

. (omitted)

valine: 3753	6.16%
GTA: 1425	2.34%
GTC: 535	0.88%
GTG: 558	0.92%
GTT: 1235	2.03%

query: print the 3-mer decomposition of
query: cds in Vaccinia.

The response is:

AAA: 7572	4.15%
AAC: 3493	1.92%
AAG: 3180	1.74%
AAT: 6247	3.42%

. (omitted)

TTC: 3031	1.66%
TTG: 2889	1.58%
TTT: 5086	2.79%

(8) Conducting basic curating functions with the "undo" facility. The assembly of a genome requires a domain expert who has sufficient knowledge of the

genetics and an understanding of how the data was derived. That curator would begin by gathering genetic and physical mapping data to assemble a view of the genome. This task requires tools that allow consistent mapping of features to the constituent fragments that will be melded. A melding tool is needed to generate contigs that accurately reflect the features assigned to the constituents. We also need a means of backing out of changes to the genome view (i.e., of "rolling back") as new information becomes available. The GRACE system accomplishes all of these tasks through the use of an update log that records the necessary manipulations of sequence assignments and assembly in memory. This allows nondestructive manipulations that can be reversed at any time. Access is also provided to established sequence comparison programs to allow the curator to check the fragment assembly process. This set of curator's tools is thoroughly described in the users manual.

(9) Handling related objects (a meager start). Two sample queries in this area are shown below.

```
query: print all objects related to cds fliC
of Salmonella.
```

The response is:

```
cds fliC of E.coli
(location=
  sequence_fragment fliCecoM[101,1597]
  complement):
  accession: EG10321
  SwissProt: P04949
```

```
query: print all objects related as
query: same_function to fliC of Salmonella.
```

2 possible interpretations

```
1: print all objects related as same_function
to cds fliC of Salmonella
2: print all objects related as same_function
to mapped_gene fliC of Salmonella
```

Which would you like? [1]: 2

The response is:

```
mapped_gene fliC of E.coli
(location=chromosome EC1[2017641,2017741]):
position: 4.252E+01
map: Bachmann
```

(10) Checking constituents. Melded sequence contigs are built from constituent sequences. One of the curator checks that invokes a FASTA [14] comparison to validate the assembly process is demonstrated below.

```
query: check constituents of alkBecoM.
```

The response from the query interface is:

```
alkBecoM is ok
```

```
query: check constituents of appAecoM.
```

The response is:

```
appAecoM can not be constructed from
constituents (see position 577)
  99.9% identity in 2076 nt overlap
```

(alignment produced omitted here)

This concludes our set of sample pidgin-English queries. A more complete manual on the use of the query interface is available on request. For reasons of space only a few examples have been presented here.

5 GenoGraphics and Its Use

One of the most useful functions of GRACE is the ability to construct maps of the assembled and analyzed genomic data that are used with the GenoGraphics tool. The basic functionality of the GenoGraphics system is described in detail in the GenoGraphics users' manual. It can be used to graphically peruse the results of a series of map construction procedures. Figure 1 shows a Genographics display of a series of aligned maps for the *E.coli* chromosome.

6 Conclusion

We set out to create a flexible database system that would allow the integration of several different types of genomic data. The GRACE prototype presented here has proven to be adaptable enough to allow the incorporation of data from several archival database systems as well as laboratory data supplied directly. In this paper we have provided an overview of the GRACE system. We have described how one interacts with the system, using the incorporated data from several model organisms. We have already used this system to incorporate the cosmid/YAC hybridization data and clone restriction fragment mapping data for

Figure 1: This figure shows a set of aligned maps of the genomic data for the *E. coli* chromosome. Displayed are the aligned clone collection data, a physical map of restriction enzyme cutting sites for eight different enzymes, assembled sequences, calculated G-C content, and structural gene positions. The aligned sequences and structural genes come from the EcoSeqV and EcoGene data sets [10–11]. The genetic loci map data are from Bachmann [12].

all three chromosomes of *S. pombe*, along with the complete DNA sequence for chromosome 3 of *S. cerevisiae*. The inclusion of these data sets did not require any alterations of the GRACE database objects.

We intend to continue expanding the breadth of chromosomal analysis tools that can take advantage of this database technology. We have already implemented portions of David Searls's GenLang grammar/parser for DNA sequence patterns [15, 16]. The tRNA subgrammar has been used successfully to identify all of the sequenced tRNAs that have been mapped for *E. coli*. The results of this analysis will be presented in another paper.

We also intend to expand the Prolog database "upward" so that it contains information on proteins (alignments, evolutionary relationships, and other information of the sort stored in the Swiss Protein Database, which we are currently putting into Prolog format) and on metabolic pathways. In addition, we will be adding interfaces for other existing genome database management tools, including "acedb" and other commercial DBMS systems. The goal is to provide an integrated database and analysis environment that is capable of dealing with the ever more complex questions concerning the comparisons of chromosomal organization between species.

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